

From Weights to Concepts: Data-Free Interpretability of CLIP via Singular Vector Decomposition

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<https://frangente.github.io/SITH>

Abstract

As vision-language models are deployed at scale, understanding their internal mechanisms becomes increasingly critical. Existing interpretability methods predominantly rely on activations, making them dataset-dependent, vulnerable to data bias, and often restricted to coarse head-level explanations. We introduce *SITH* (*Semantic Inspection of Transformer Heads*), a fully data-free, training-free framework that directly analyzes CLIP’s vision transformer in *weight space*. For each attention head, we decompose its value-output matrix into singular vectors and interpret each one via COMP (*Coherent Orthogonal Matching Pursuit*), a new algorithm that explains them as sparse, semantically coherent combinations of human-interpretable concepts. We show that *SITH* yields coherent, faithful intra-head explanations, validated through reconstruction fidelity and interpretability experiments. This allows us to use *SITH* for precise, interpretable weight-space model edits that amplify or suppress specific concepts, improving downstream performance without retraining. Furthermore, we use *SITH* to study model adaptation, showing how fine-tuning primarily reweights a stable semantic basis rather than learning entirely new features.

1. Introduction

Vision-Language Models (VLMs), such as CLIP [58], have demonstrated impressive capabilities in multimodal understanding and have become central to numerous practical applications [33, 76, 78]. The standard approach to VLMs has been to treat them as black boxes, focusing on their outputs rather than the underlying computational processes that produce them. However, as these models grow in scale and see broader real-world deployment, understanding how they represent and integrate concepts has become increasingly important. Mechanistic interpretability [36] seeks to shed some light on understanding neural networks by mapping internal mechanisms to human-meaningful explanations, al-

Figure 1. **Comparison between TextSpan [23] and our proposed SITH applied to CLIP’s vision transformer.** TextSpan computes attention-head activations on a large image dataset (e.g., ImageNet [15]) and aligns them with textual concepts, yielding head-level interpretations (e.g., head h_1 focuses on colors). In contrast, SITH is *data-free*: it directly decomposes each head’s weights into singular vectors and interprets them via COMP, providing fine-grained, semantically coherent explanations at the vector level (e.g., vector v_2 within h_1 specializes in color green).

lowing us to identify which sub-components are responsible for the outputs of downstream tasks.

Despite significant advances in model interpretability, mechanistic understanding of VLMs remains an open problem. Previous works proposed to investigate the output representation of CLIP vision transformer layers [2, 52, 61] or of its attention heads [23] by associating intermediate model activations with human-interpretable concepts, as those features lie in the shared vision-language space. While such approaches have provided valuable insights into CLIP, they either explain how single samples are represented, or extract only coarse-grained descriptions of entire attention heads. Moreover, as these methods depend on large-scale datasets to derive activations, their interpretation of model components is inherently influenced by dataset biases (Fig. 1, top).

Table 1. Comparison between prior works and our SITH.

	Training-free	Data-free	Explanation Granularity
SAE [52, 61, 80]	✗	✗	Sample-level
TextSpan [23]	✓	✗	Head-level
SITH (Ours)	✓	✓	Intra-head (singular vector)

Motivated by these challenges, this work introduces SITH (Semantic Inspection of Transformer Heads), a novel approach to mechanistic interpretability that does not depend on model activations and directly analyzes the weights of CLIP’s attention heads (Fig. 1, bottom).

SITH builds on the seminal work of Elhage et al. [20], which shows that the computation performed by an attention head can be expressed as a weighted combination of its input patches transformed by the head’s value-output (VO) weight matrix. Leveraging this insight, SITH decomposes the attention head’s VO matrix using Singular Value Decomposition (SVD) [19], revealing its dominant computational directions. Then, to interpret these directions semantically, we propose Coherent Orthogonal Matching Pursuit (COMP), a novel decomposition algorithm representing each singular vector as a sparse, positive combination of textual concepts, optimizing both reconstruction fidelity and semantic coherence.

SITH’s weight-based perspective offers several key advantages. As shown in Tab. 1, our approach is entirely training-free, requiring no additional optimization to obtain concept interpretations. Second, SITH is data-free, as it does not depend on any dataset or model activations to derive the interpretations, thus avoiding dataset-induced biases. Third, by analyzing singular vectors rather than entire heads, it enables a more fine-grained dissection of the model’s knowledge, allowing us to isolate and intervene on individual semantic subspaces encoded within a head.

By applying SITH to the visual encoder of CLIP, we find that individual singular vectors map to distinct, human-interpretable concepts, such as textures, locations, backgrounds, and colors (Sec. 4). These findings enable precise, concept-level interventions: by amplifying or suppressing specific singular vectors, we can reduce the model’s sensitivity to spurious correlations (Sec. 5.1), suppress undesired concepts (Sec. 5.2), and improve performance on downstream tasks (Sec. 5.3), all without the need for training or data. Moreover, SITH provides a compelling lens into model adaptation (Sec. 6). It exposes how fine-tuning subtly reorients the model’s feature basis toward the semantic space of the target task, with changes that align with the fine-tuning objective. In summary, our contributions are:

- We propose SITH, a data-free, training-free, and weight-based interpretability framework that provides input-independent explanations of CLIP’s attention heads.
- SITH achieves fine-grained explanations by decomposing model weights into singular vectors and associating them

with human-interpretable concepts via COMP, our novel sparse decomposition technique.

- We demonstrate how SITH can benefit downstream applications via data-free interventions that suppress spurious correlations, reduce sensitivity to unsafe content, and improve classification performance.
- We use SITH to analyze model adaptation, showing that fine-tuning introduces meaningful, task-specific directional changes without altering the overall structure of the learned feature basis.

2. Related works

Mechanistic Interpretability aims to uncover how neural networks operate internally by examining their core components and the computational pathways they form. This can be done either by studying model responses to input features (*activation-based* interpretability) or by inspecting its weights directly (*weight-based* interpretability).

Activation-based interpretability studies initially focused on individual neurons [9, 27, 46–48]. However, interpreting neuron representations is difficult, especially in large models, as neurons often exist in a state of superposition [21], simultaneously encoding multiple unrelated concepts. Sparse Autoencoders (SAEs) project hidden representations into a sparse set of features that ideally align with human-interpretable concepts [5, 7, 8, 13, 24, 59, 60], and have been used to analyze both language [30, 79] and multimodal models [34, 38, 52, 61, 68, 70, 80]. However, SAEs exhibit severe instability, as models trained on similar datasets can produce entirely different dictionaries [22]. Moreover, the encoding of hierarchical concepts within SAEs is often fragile: seemingly monosemantic features fail to activate when expected, with their activations instead being absorbed by child features [11]. Gandselman et al. [23] proposed interpreting the attention heads of CLIP’s vision transformer by aligning their output activations across images with a set of textual concepts. This approach revealed that several attention heads specialize in specific semantic roles, such as colors, numbers, and geographic locations. However, like all activation-based methods, it requires large-scale datasets (e.g. ImageNet [15]) to collect activations from all model components for analysis (see Tab. 1). Moreover the resulting explanations are coarse-grained, as they identify which concepts are represented by a head but do not specify which internal features encode those concepts.

Weight-based interpretability addresses these limitations by directly analyzing the model’s weights to reliably uncover learned features [74]. While applying parameter decomposition or spectral analysis to Transformer weights has prior precedent, existing works do so under different assumptions and goals. For instance, Braun et al. [4] and Bushnaq et al. [6] learn data-dependent factorizations, whereas existing SVD-based analyses focus on understanding inter-layer com-

Figure 2. **Overview of SITH and COMP.** (left) SITH isolates the **Value-Output** (VO) matrix of a CLIP ViT attention head and factorizes it via Singular Value Decomposition (SVD), yielding singular vectors $\{v_j\}$ that capture the head’s dominant writing directions. Given a textual concept pool Γ processed by CLIP’s text encoder \mathcal{E}_T , each vector is then explained using COMP, yielding sparse and coherent per-vector interpretations (e.g., “green”, “mint green”, and “grass green”). (right) COMP iteratively decomposes a **target singular vector** \hat{v}_j as a sparse, non-negative combination of **concept embeddings** $\hat{\Gamma}$. In Iteration 1 it selects the **concept** with the highest similarity to the **target**. The **residual vector** \star captures the remaining, unexplained part of the original **vector**. From Iteration 2 to K , COMP repeatedly chooses additional concepts that are both close to the current **residual** and **semantically consistent** with the accumulated **concept set** (see Eq. (7)). This process continues until the sparsity budget K is reached.

munication [40], the geometric properties of weights [66], or the local/global behavior of attention [53]. Furthermore, works analyzing the features encoded by weights [14, 26] or singular vectors [42] via token-space projections remain limited to unimodal language models and rely on simple nearest-neighbor searches, which fail to capture the full semantic content, leading to incomplete interpretations. In contrast, we propose a coherence-regularized sparse coding algorithm to map singular vectors into complete and human-interpretable explanations. We then use these decompositions within an end-to-end, data-free interpretability framework for VLMs, enabling fine-grained intra-head concept attribution and direct singular-value editing at scale.

3. SITH: Interpreting CLIP Weights

SITH associates features from the heads of the CLIP Vision Transformer with human-interpretable concepts drawn from an overcomplete pool $\Gamma = \{\gamma_1, \dots, \gamma_C\}$. Unlike prior works [23], we extract such features from the model *weights* directly, without requiring additional data. We begin by reviewing the CLIP architecture, the residual stream formulation, and how to isolate the contribution of each attention head (Sec. 3.1). Then, we apply SVD [19] to the attention head’s value-output matrix, revealing the dominant directions of information flow within each head (Sec. 3.2). Finally, we propose COMP, a sparse concept attribution method that maps these directions to interpretable natural language concepts γ , enabling a compact and human-aligned interpretation of the attention heads (Sec. 3.3). We provide a visualization of our method in Fig. 2.

3.1. Preliminaries

CLIP (Contrastive Language-Image Pretraining) [58] maps images and text into a shared embedding space $\subseteq \mathbb{R}^d$ using an image encoder \mathcal{E}_I and a text encoder \mathcal{E}_T , trained in a contrastive learning fashion. Following recent works [23, 82], we focus on CLIP models whose vision backbone is based on the Vision Transformer (ViT) [17] architecture. Given an image I , \mathcal{E}_I first splits it into P non-overlapping patches, which are projected into D -dimensional tokens and summed to positional embeddings. Then, a learnable [CLS] token is prepended to the image patches, resulting in a sequence $\mathbf{X}^0 \in \mathbb{R}^{(P+1) \times D}$ with $x_{\text{CLS}}^0, x_1^0, x_2^0, \dots, x_P^0$ as rows, that is processed by L transformer layers. Each layer l computes its output \mathbf{X}^l via two residual updates:

$$\hat{\mathbf{X}}^l = \text{MHA}^l(\text{LN}(\mathbf{X}^{l-1})) + \mathbf{X}^{l-1} \quad (1)$$

$$\mathbf{X}^l = \text{FFN}^l(\text{LN}(\hat{\mathbf{X}}^l)) + \hat{\mathbf{X}}^l, \quad (2)$$

where MHA and FFN are the multi-head attention module and feed-forward network components, while LN is a layer normalization operation. Finally, the CLIP representation $\mathcal{E}_I(I) \in \mathbb{R}^d$ of the image I is obtained by projecting the final [CLS] token output x_{CLS}^L through a learned matrix $\mathbf{W}_p \in \mathbb{R}^{D \times d}$.

Residual stream decomposition. We can express the output of the [CLS] token after L transformer layers as the sum of its initial embedding and the direct contributions from each layer through the residual stream [23]:

$$x_{\text{CLS}}^L = x_{\text{CLS}}^0 + \sum_{l=1}^L \left(\text{MHA}^l(\mathbf{X}^{l-1})_{\text{CLS}} + \text{FFN}^l(\hat{\mathbf{X}}^l)_{\text{CLS}} \right), \quad (3)$$

where the affine parameters of the LN are folded into the adjacent projection matrices [20] (see Supp. Mat., Sec. A

for details). This enables a clean separation of contributions from the [CLS] token, the MHA, and the FFN modules.

Decomposing Attention Heads. Following Elhage et al. [20], the multi-head attention can be expressed as the sum of the outputs of H independent attention heads:

$$\text{MHA}(\mathbf{X}) = \sum_{h=1}^H \mathbf{A}^h \mathbf{X} \mathbf{W}_{VO}^h, \quad (4)$$

where \mathbf{A}^h is the attention matrix for head h , and $\mathbf{W}_{VO}^h \in \mathbb{R}^{D \times D}$ is the value-output (VO) weight matrix for head h obtained by combining its value \mathbf{W}_V^h and output \mathbf{W}_O^h projection matrices as $\mathbf{W}_{VO}^h := \mathbf{W}_V^h \mathbf{W}_O^h$ (refer to Sec. A of the Supp. Mat. for additional details).

While both the attention pattern \mathbf{A}^h and VO matrix \mathbf{W}_{VO}^h drive a head’s computation, they play distinct roles. \mathbf{A}^h acts as a router deciding how information flows between tokens (e.g., from an “apple” patch to the [CLS] token), while \mathbf{W}_{VO}^h determines which information is moved (e.g., reading “redness” from the source and writing it to the destination’s residual stream). Hence, by isolating \mathbf{W}_{VO}^h , we gain an input-independent understanding of the specific semantic features a head can extract and write.

3.2. Finding Principal Directions with SVD

As stated above, analyzing the \mathbf{W}_{VO}^h (hereafter \mathbf{W}_{VO} for ease of notation) of an attention head provides insight into how the head transforms information within the residual stream. Because the VO matrix is a linear transformation, its behavior can be characterized in terms of the directions along which it most strongly amplifies or suppresses information. To capture these dominant axes, we propose to factorize the VO matrix using Singular Value Decomposition (SVD) [19], yielding:

$$\mathbf{W}_{VO} = \mathbf{U} \mathbf{\Sigma} \mathbf{V}^T \quad (5)$$

where, \mathbf{U} and \mathbf{V} are $D \times r$ semi-orthogonal matrices, with $r = \text{rank}(\mathbf{W}_{VO})$, whose columns are the left singular vectors $\{\mathbf{u}_i\}$ and right singular vectors $\{\mathbf{v}_i\}$, respectively. $\mathbf{\Sigma}$ is a diagonal matrix of non-negative singular values $\sigma_i \geq 0$, sorted in descending order.

Intuitively, each left singular vector \mathbf{u}_i defines an input direction in the residual stream that the head reads from, while the corresponding right singular vector \mathbf{v}_i defines an output direction in the residual stream that the head writes to. The associated singular value σ_i quantifies how strongly the head maps the input direction \mathbf{u}_i to the output direction \mathbf{v}_i . Thus, by analyzing the singular vectors, we can identify the most significant features that the attention head is capable of extracting and writing back to the residual stream¹.

¹Note that the effective contribution of a writing direction \mathbf{v}_i to the residual stream is also influenced by how well input tokens align with the corresponding reading direction \mathbf{u}_i , and by the attention scores.

3.3. Semantic Interpretation via COMP

Since the singular vectors lie in the same semantic space of the image embeddings, we can leverage the embedding space of CLIP to semantically interpret them. More formally, given the right singular matrix \mathbf{V}^T (and analogously for the left singular matrix \mathbf{U}), let $\hat{\mathbf{V}}^T = \mathbf{V}^T \mathbf{W}_p$ be the singular vectors projected into the CLIP multimodal space². We can identify those concepts in the concept pool Γ which better correspond to the semantic content of each singular vector by computing the cosine similarity between $\hat{\mathbf{v}}$ and the concept embeddings $\hat{\Gamma} = \mathcal{E}_T(\Gamma) \in \mathbb{R}^{C \times d}$, and choosing the *top-k* most similar concepts.

While this approach provides a basic interpretation, we found it often fails to capture the full semantic content of the singular vectors. This is particularly true when the concept pool lacks an exact match for the singular vector, leading to incomplete or misleading interpretations. For instance, a singular vector representing “a red apple” may be ambiguously mapped to either “apple” or “red” if those are the only available concepts, thus missing the combined meaning.

To address this problem, we propose to express each singular vector $\hat{\mathbf{v}}$ as a sparse, non-negative linear combination of concept embeddings $\hat{\Gamma}$, by finding a sparse coefficient vector $\mathbf{c} \in \mathbb{R}^C$ that solves the following L_0 -minimization problem:

$$\min_{\mathbf{c}} \|\mathbf{c}\|_0 \quad \text{subject to} \quad \|\hat{\mathbf{v}} - \hat{\Gamma}^T \mathbf{c}\|_2^2 \leq \epsilon \quad \text{and} \quad \mathbf{c} \geq 0 \quad (6)$$

with $\mathbf{c} \geq 0$ ensuring that each singular vector is expressed in terms of its constituent concepts [2].

A standard greedy algorithm for this problem is Non-Negative Orthogonal Matching Pursuit (NNOMP) [55]. Let S_k denote the indices of the support set of concepts selected up to step k , and let \mathbf{r}_k be the residual vector, *i.e.* the reconstruction error of the target vector $\hat{\mathbf{v}}$ at step k using $\hat{\Gamma}_{S_k}$ as the reconstruction basis. Starting with an empty support set S_0 and initial residual $\mathbf{r}_0 = \hat{\mathbf{v}}$, NNOMP proceeds iteratively as follows: (1) select the concept $\hat{\gamma}_i$ from the vocabulary with the highest correlation score $\langle \mathbf{r}_{k-1}, \hat{\gamma}_i \rangle$, (2) add i to the support set S_k , (3) update the coefficients \mathbf{c} by solving a non-negative least squares problem over the selected concepts $\hat{\Gamma}_{S_k}$, and (4) update the residual \mathbf{r}_k using $\mathbf{r}_k = \hat{\mathbf{v}} - \hat{\Gamma}_{S_k}^T \mathbf{c}$. This process is iteratively repeated until a stopping criterion is met, such as reaching a target sparsity level K or achieving a sufficiently small residual norm.

A key limitation of this selection strategy (step 1) is that it solely optimizes for reconstruction error, which can lead to a semantically incoherent set of concepts, thus making the final explanation harder to interpret.

To address this, we introduce **Coherent Orthogonal Matching Pursuit (COMP)**, an algorithm that modifies the

²To mitigate the multimodality gap of CLIP, we follow the approach of Bhalla et al. [2]; see Sec. A of the Supp. Mat.

Figure 3. **Interpretability and fidelity scores of SITH evaluated under varying sparsity levels** using different decomposition strategies: our proposed COMP, NNOMP [55], and top-k.

scoring function in the concept selection step to explicitly balance reconstruction quality with semantic coherence. In COMP, given residual \mathbf{r}_{k-1} and support set S_{k-1} , the concept selection criterion at iteration k is replaced by the following scoring function:

$$\text{score}(\hat{\gamma}_i) = \underbrace{\langle \mathbf{r}_{k-1}, \hat{\gamma}_i \rangle}_{\text{Reconstruction Term}} + \frac{\lambda}{|S_{k-1}|} \sum_{j \in S_{k-1}} \underbrace{\langle \hat{\gamma}_i, \hat{\gamma}_j \rangle}_{\text{Coherence Term}}, \quad (7)$$

where *Reconstruction Term* is the standard NNOMP criterion, *i.e.*, selecting concepts that align with the unexplained portion of the target singular vector, and the *Coherence Term* is a novel regularizer that measures the average semantic similarity between a candidate concept $\hat{\gamma}_i$ and all concepts $\hat{\gamma}_j$ already chosen. This term encourages the selection of new concepts that are semantically related to the concepts already in the support set. The hyperparameter $\lambda \geq 0$ controls this trade-off. When $\lambda = 0$, COMP recovers standard NNOMP. As λ increases, the algorithm increasingly favors semantic coherence, producing a sparse set of concepts that is not only reconstructive but also forms a more interpretable and meaningful explanation. We provide the pseudocode of COMP in Sec. E of the Supp. Mat.

4. Evaluating SITH

For a given attention head $h \in [1, H]$ within transformer layer $l \in [1, L]$, SITH analyzes it by decomposing its VO matrix $\mathbf{W}_{VO}^{l,h}$ into r singular vectors, and linking each singular vector to K concepts. Here we show that such concept sets provide highly coherent and human-interpretable explanations, while remaining faithful to the original semantic information encoded within the vectors.

Experimental setting. Following Gandelsman et al. [23], we focus our analysis on the last 4 layers of the OpenCLIP ViT-L/14 model [32] ($L = 24$, $H = 16$, $r = 64$) pretrained

Table 2. Examples of singular vectors from the last four layers of ViT-L/14 along with their reconstructed concepts using SITH with COMP ($\lambda = 0.3$, $K = 5$). The numbers in parentheses indicate the coefficients assigned to each concept in the reconstruction.

Layer 23, Head 8, SV 0 🍷	Layer 22, Head 7, SV 0 🧑
pink red (0.3144)	late december (0.1900)
red telephone (0.1571)	winterwear (0.1833)
red and white factors (0.1503)	barren trees in winter (0.1729)
scarlet reds (0.1473)	winter buds (0.1554)
red background (0.1369)	winter in valley (0.1383)
Layer 21, Head 11, SV 3 🌊	Layer 20, Head 4, SV 0 🧑
ocean beach (0.1334)	two girls (0.2121)
surf culture (0.1170)	doublepack (0.2065)
sandiego (0.1116)	two combatants (0.1902)
catalina island (0.1069)	comedy duos (0.1666)
southern california (0.0213)	two credit cards (0.1612)

on the LAION-2B dataset [64]. We use ConceptNet 5.5 [67] as our concept dictionary (see Sec. B of the Supp. Mat. for additional dictionaries) and use GPT-5-mini [51] for those experiments requiring an LLM (see Sec. F of the Supp. Mat. for the exact prompts). Our analysis focuses on the right singular vectors $\mathbf{v}_i \in \mathbf{V}$, as they correspond to the output directions of each head and thus have a direct effect on the final image representation. Refer to Sec. C of the Supp. Mat. for analysis on the left singular vectors $\mathbf{u}_i \in \mathbf{U}$.

4.1. Interpretability-Fidelity Analysis

For a decomposition to be useful, the set of concepts associated with a singular vector must satisfy two competing criteria: (i) *fidelity*, the degree to which the concepts faithfully capture the semantic information embedded in the vector; and (ii) *interpretability*, the extent to which the concepts can be understood as a coherent explanation. Fidelity is quantified via cosine similarity between the original vector and its reconstruction using our extracted concepts (see Supp. Mat., Sec. A for computation of the reconstructed vector), while interpretability is assessed using an LLM-as-a-judge rating the coherence of the concept set on a 5-point Likert scale. A rating of 1 indicates semantically unrelated or incoherent concepts (*e.g.*, “vintage toaster” and “hiking”), whereas a rating of 5 denotes a highly coherent and conceptually aligned grouping (*e.g.*, “cat” and “feline fur”).

In Fig. 3, we report results for SITH using COMP across varying values of the regularization parameter $\lambda \in \{0.2, 0.3, 0.4\}$, and the number of selected concepts $K \in \{5, 10, 20, 50\}$ on the last layer ($l = 23$; see Supp. Mat., Sec. C for results on all other tested layers). For comparison, we also consider two alternative decomposition strategies, replacing COMP with non-negative orthogonal matching pursuit (NNOMP) [55] and a naive top- k selection of the most similar concepts. The top- k strategy naturally retrieves

Figure 4. **Zero-shot classification accuracy when replacing the original singular vectors of layer $l = 23$ with their reconstructions** using different numbers of concepts and across different datasets [15, 35, 45, 54]. We also report the accuracy of the original OpenCLIP model, and its accuracy when all heads of the layer are zeroed-out (*i.e.*, Zero-ablation).

highly coherent concept sets, but it struggles with completeness: it yields poor reconstructions that do not improve significantly even when increasing K , as it only captures a narrow slice of the singular vector’s semantic content. In contrast, NNOMP achieves strong reconstruction performance but sacrifices interpretability, often selecting disjointed and less coherent concept sets even at low sparsity levels $K = 5$. Our proposed COMP achieves an optimal balance between completeness and coherence, offering reconstructions that closely match original singular vectors while maintaining semantically cohesive, human-interpretable explanations.

Qualitative results of the resulting concept sets along with the weight attributed to each concept can be found in Tab. 2 (see Sec. D of the Supp. Mat. for further qualitative results). It is important to note that none of the methods perfectly reconstruct all singular vectors, even at high values of $K = 50$. This is likely due to certain singular vectors encoding not only semantic concepts, but also non-semantic or task-irrelevant “noisy” information that cannot be linked to human-interpretable concepts, as suggested in prior work [2]. However, this phenomenon does not adversely affect downstream performance. As shown in Fig. 4, substituting the original singular vectors with their SITH-based reconstructions results in negligible degradation in zero-shot classification accuracy across multiple benchmarks [15, 35, 45, 54].

4.2. Grounding Singular Vectors to Images

To further verify that SITH not only successfully reconstructs singular vectors, but also captures their actual visual focus, we conduct an image matching experiment on the large-scale CC12M dataset [10]. For each image, we compute the similarity between the image embedding at layer l and each singular vector. We then rank images by similarity to each vector and retrieve the top matches. As illustrated in Fig. 5, the retrieved images exhibit strong conceptual alignment with the semantic explanations assigned by SITH, suggesting that the attributed meanings are indeed grounded in visual evidence. To further quantify this alignment, we

Figure 5. **Top-3 images matched to a singular vector.** Each cell shows the top-3 images from CC12M [10] that are most similar to a specific singular vector, along with the interpretation of that singular vector. See Sec. D of Supp. Mat. for additional examples.

run an experiment where we ask a vision-LLM-as-a-judge to rate the correspondence between every set of retrieved images and their singular vector interpretation (see Sec. F of the Supp. Mat. for the complete prompt). As shown in Fig. 6, SITH achieves consistently high matching scores across the final four layers of the model, particularly the last one. We also evaluate TextSpan [23] under the same setting with both its original concept dictionary and ConceptNet 5.5 [67], showing that it yields coarser explanations that fail to capture the full function of the attention head. These results demonstrate that SITH produces fine-grained, coherent explanations for individual vectors, capturing distinct, interpretable visual functions.

5. SITH Enables Interpretable Model Editing

One of the many strengths of SITH is its ability to enable *controlled editing of a model’s behavior* through a fine-grained decomposition of internal representations. By adjusting the singular values associated with specific singular vectors, we can directly modulate how much the model relies on particular features or concepts during inference. To determine which components to edit, we use an LLM [51] to evaluate the relevance of each concept set for a given downstream task, guiding the amplification or suppression of singular values. This provides a lightweight, interpretable, and data-

Figure 6. **Mean image-concept agreement scores** across the last four layers of OpenCLIP [32]. * replaces the original concept pool of TextSpan [23] with ConceptNet 5.5 [67].

Table 3. **Zero-shot classification accuracy on Waterbirds [62]** before and after suppressing spurious features. * indicates recomputed with zero-ablation of heads for zero-shot comparison. “Random” refers to average performance obtained by randomly ablating same number of singular values as our method, averaged over 5 runs.

	Overall	Worst-group
OpenCLIP [32]	73.5	47.9
w/ Random	72.0	45.1
w/ TextSpan* [23]	81.8	68.0
w/ SITH (Ours)	82.7	70.6

free alternative to *singular value fine-tuning* [69], requiring no training data or gradient updates. In the following, we show how SITH can be applied to mitigate spurious correlations (Sec. 5.1), suppress unsafe concepts (Sec. 5.2), and to improve zero-shot classification accuracy (Sec. 5.3).

5.1. Suppressing Spurious Correlations

We can use the concepts provided by SITH to identify and suppress features corresponding to confounding factors that should not influence predictions. We follow Gandselman et al. [23] and test SITH on the Waterbirds classification dataset [62], which contains birds on backgrounds that do not correspond to their natural habitats. As shown in Tab. 3, by removing the singular vectors whose concepts are related to background information (*i.e.*, setting their corresponding singular values to 0, see Sec. A of Supp. Mat. for additional details), we obtain a significant improvement, both in terms of overall accuracy and worst-group accuracy. Notably, our method outperforms TextSpan [23], highlighting the advantage of surgically editing only the subcomponents of an attention head, rather than removing entire heads.

5.2. Removing NSFW Concepts

SITH can also enhance the safety of CLIP by suppressing its ability to process NSFW (Not Safe For Work) concepts

Table 4. **Retrieval R@10 results on the ViSU [57] test set.** Left columns show text-to-image and image-to-text performance when using textual and visual safe queries (*i.e.*, **T** and **V**, respectively) on a pool of both safe and unsafe data. Right columns use unsafe textual and visual queries (*i.e.*, **T*** and **V***, respectively). † Safe-CLIP [32] is a training-based method specific for NSFW removal that uses OpenAI-CLIP [58] pretraining.

	Safe Query		Unsafe Query	
	T →(V ∪ V*)	V →(T ∪ T*)	T* →(V ∪ V*)	V* →(T ∪ T*)
Safe-CLIP† [57]	69.2	73.9	46.3	62.3
OpenCLIP [32]	75.1	77.0	29.3	38.9
w/ SITH (Ours)	74.5	77.3	29.5	40.4

Table 5. **Zero-shot classification accuracy on various datasets** before and after editing the model by amplifying/suppressing specific singular values.

	Flowers 102 [45]	FGVC-Aircraft [39]	DTD [12]
OpenCLIP [32]	76.5	36.6	50.1
w/ Random	76.4	36.3	49.9
w/ SITH (Ours)	77.5	36.9	50.9

such as nudity or violence. This is achieved by identifying and suppressing the specific singular vectors associated with these undesired terms (see Sec. A of the Supp. Mat. for additional details). To evaluate the effectiveness of our intervention, we replicate the image-text retrieval experiment conducted by Poppi et al. [57] on the ViSU dataset, which includes paired safe and unsafe image-caption samples. The objective is to ensure that, regardless of the query term (*i.e.*, image or text) being safe or unsafe, the model preferentially retrieves the corresponding safe content only. As shown in Tab. 4, our modified CLIP demonstrates improved retrieval accuracy compared to the unmodified baseline, particularly when handling unsafe queries. Notably, it even outperforms Safe-CLIP [57], a model specifically trained for safety, when the input queries are safe.

5.3. Improving Classification Performance

While Secs. 5.1 and 5.2 address the suppression of undesirable concepts, here we aim to amplify features that are beneficial for a specific downstream classification task. Given a task and its class labels, we compute a similarity score between the concept set of each singular vector and the class names. We then rescale each singular value by a factor proportional to its similarity with the task, thus amplifying the contribution of relevant concepts and suppressing that of irrelevant ones (see Sec. A of the Supp. Mat. for details). As shown in Tab. 5, this simple intervention leads to consistent improvements across three different datasets [12, 39, 45], achieving gains of up to 1.0 points. In contrast, randomly selecting the scaling factors leads to consistent performance degradation. These results underscore the effectiveness of SITH for data-free singular value fine-tuning [69], enabling

Figure 7. **Changes in the attention heads after model adaptation.** For each attention head (*i.e.* square in the plot) of the last four layers of CLIP ViT-L/14, we report the normalized spectral cosine similarity [1] between the right singular vectors of the pre-trained (\mathbf{W}_{VO}^{pre}) and finetuned (\mathbf{W}_{VO}^{ft}) matrices of that head, across different fine-tuning datasets and adaptation methods. High values correspond to subtle shifts in the head after fine-tuning.

Figure 8. **Analysis of $\Delta\mathbf{W}$ with SITH after model adaptation.** Using an LLM-as-a-judge we compute the percentage of task singular vectors [25] aligned with the fine-tuning domain across different benchmarks and adaptation methods.

task-aware model adaptation without requiring labeled data.

6. Interpreting Model Adaptation Techniques

A key open question in mechanistic interpretability is understanding how pre-trained models adapt to new tasks through fine-tuning [65]. Here we show how SITH can be used as a tool to dissect the semantic changes induced by fine-tuning. Specifically, we finetune CLIP ViT-L/14 on three fine-grained classification datasets (Flowers 102 [45], Oxford Pets [54], and CUB-200 [75]) and compare the original and finetuned attention head weights (\mathbf{W}_{VO}^{pre} and \mathbf{W}_{VO}^{ft} , respectively). To ensure our findings are not specific to full fine-tuning, we repeat our analysis also using LoRA [29] (see Sec. A of the Supp. Mat. for further details).

Fine-tuning Induces a Subtle Subspace Shift. To measure the geometric change to the value-output matrix induced by fine-tuning, we compute the SVD of both \mathbf{W}_{VO}^{pre} and \mathbf{W}_{VO}^{ft} and compare their right singular vector subspaces using normalized spectral cosine similarity [1]. As seen in Fig. 7, the singular vectors remain remarkably stable across all adaptation methods, indicating that fine-tuning does not drastically alter the learned semantic basis, but rather applies a slight modification to the pre-trained weights.

The Fine-tuning Delta is Semantically Aligned. To verify whether the subtle changes induced by fine-tuning have coherent semantic directions, we analyze the task singular vectors [25] (*i.e.*, the singular vectors of the difference matrix $\Delta\mathbf{W} = \mathbf{W}_{VO}^{ft} - \mathbf{W}_{VO}^{pre}$) using our COMP method. We asked an LLM to classify whether the explanations obtained by COMP for the task singular vectors are relevant to the fine-tuning domain. As shown in Fig. 8, the majority of the task singular vectors are indeed aligned with the fine-tuning task across all datasets and adaptation methods. For instance, when fine-tuning on Flowers 102, the top task singular vectors are associated to concepts from the plant domain, such as “alpine flowers”, “oriental photinia”, and “camelia flower”. We observe similar patterns also for the other two tasks, with Oxford Pets yielding concepts like “english bulldog”, “bordeaux mastiff”, and “egyptian mau”, and CUB-200 producing bird-related concepts, including “black catbird”, “red legged tinamous”, and “chiffchaff”.

7. Conclusion

We introduced SITH, a novel data-free and training-free framework for interpreting the internal features used by CLIP’s vision transformer. By applying Singular Value Decomposition directly to the Value-Output (VO) weight matrices, we isolated the computational directions within each attention head. We proposed COMP, a decomposition algorithm that translates these singular vectors into sparse, semantically coherent combinations of human-interpretable concepts. We demonstrated that this intra-head level of analysis is not only faithful and interpretable but also enables precise, interpretable model edits to suppress spurious correlations, remove undesirable content, and enhance downstream task performance without retraining. Additionally, it enables understanding that weights’ updates are task-aligned during fine-tuning on downstream tasks.

Future work will extend the analysis to other components of VLMs, such as FFN layers, and to the Query-Key matrices to better understand how attention patterns arise from semantic features.

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